

THE ROLE OF BRAND IMAGE IN MEDIATING THE EFFECTS OF PRODUCT QUALITY AND SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the direct and indirect effects of brand image, price, product quality and service quality on customer loyalty at the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. This study used quantitative analysis with a sample consisting of 172 respondents who were selected using non-probability sampling. The data analysis used is SEM-PLS. The results showed that the four variables, namely brand image, price, product quality, and service quality, directly had a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty, as well as price and product quality directly had a significant effect on brand image, but service quality did not have a significant effect on brand image at the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. It is also shown that indirectly brand image can mediate the effect of price and service quality on customer loyalty, but brand image cannot mediate the effect of service quality on customer loyalty at the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan.

Keywords: Brand Image, Price, Product Quality, Service Quality, Customer Loyalty

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the automotive industry in Indonesia began when, in 1969, the Ministry of Industry and Trade issued a joint regulation on the import of motorized vehicles, either completely built-up (CBU) or completely knocked down (CKD) as well as on the assembly and agency. At that time assembly industries and supporting industries began to emerge, such as spare parts, painting, batteries (accumulators). Local industries are already capable of producing jigs and fixtures, as well as carrying out painting, welding, trimming and metal finishing processes (Gaikindo.or.id). Automotive products in Indonesia are dominated by automotive products from Japan with various brands, namely Toyota, Daihatsu, Honda, Mitsubishi, Mazda, Suzuki, and Nissan which have been able to enliven the automotive market in Indonesia. Most of these automotive brands from Japan do not directly set up their factories as production bases in Indonesia, but also export their cars as a whole to Indonesia. Toyota's ability to consistently produce its cars is able to influence the attractiveness of the people and the Government of Indonesia to cooperate with the Toyota Motor Corporation so that they can enter Indonesia and be able to produce Toyota cars in Indonesia (Gaikindo.or.id). Noting that the automotive market segment from Japan has huge potential in the Indonesian market so that it becomes a struggle between businessmen from Indonesia, the Government of Indonesia changed the business map for the invasion of cars from Japan to Indonesia with a scheme requiring the establishment of a Brand Sole Agent. The regulations made by the Government of Indonesia have been established since 1968. These regulations do not only

apply to car manufacturers from Japan but to all manufacturers that will enter Indonesia (Mohammad, 2013).

Figure 1: Development of Car Sales in Indonesia 2009-2021

The development of sales of all types of cars shows fluctuations every year, but it can be seen that car sales in Indonesia after 2009 showed a considerable increase, even in 2020 which was affected by Covid-19, car sales were still higher than in 2009. Over time, Toyota has become the leader in the automotive market in Indonesia. Based on data for 2009 – 2021, Toyota remains the market leader even though it shows a decline every year. In 2009 Toyota's market share was 78.18% and continued to decline, until in 2021 the market share became 33.27%, but remained the market leader.

Toyota Sales (in Thousands of Units)

Figure 2: Market Shares of Car Sales in Indonesia in 2021 (Gaikindo.or.id)

The phenomena that occur in the automotive industry in Indonesia can be seen based on sales data for car types which are still controlled by the Toyota brand with a market share of > 30% (Gaikindo, 2021). For decades, Toyota has been the market leader in car sales in Indonesia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND SUBMISSION OF HYPOTHESIS

2.1 Customer Loyalty

Loyalty comes from the word loyal which means faithful (Sudarso, 2016). According to the Oxford English Dictionary, “Loyalty is a strong feeling of support and allegiance” (Stevenson, 2010). Loyalty is a reaction or behavior/purchase that is biased which is reflected continuously by decision makers by paying attention to one or more choices from a number of similar brands and is a function of the psychological process of feelings in it (Sugiharti, 2012). Kotler and Keller (2016) define consumer loyalty as a deeply held commitment to rebuy or repatronize a preferred product or service in the future despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behavior. Where in this case loyalty is a commitment that is held to buy or reuse the preferred product or service in the future even though there is the influence of the situation and marketing actions or efforts to switch. Meanwhile, Tjiptono (2014) describes that customer loyalty is a customer commitment to a brand, store, or supplier. According to Subaebasni et al., (2018), customer loyalty means that customers decide to consistently use the same brand because they like the service or product quality they receive. This is confirmed by Chiguvi & Guruwo (2018) that customer loyalty is defined as a commitment to continue buying the preferred product or service consistently regardless of situational factors and marketing efforts that may result in switching behavior. According to Griffin (2016), a loyal customer has a specific bias about what to buy and from whom. Two important conditions associated with loyalty and total share of customer. Many companies operate under the false impression that a retained customer is automatically a loyal customer. Loyalty is defined as non-random purchase expressed over time by some decision-making unit. A loyal customer is one who makes regular repeat purchases, purchase across product lines, refers others and demonstrates on immunity to the pull of the competition. Loyal consumers are consumers who have the characteristics of, among others, making purchases or using products/services repeatedly at the same business entity, purchasing or using product lines and services offered by the same business entity. Loyalty has been recognized as the dominant factor influencing business success today. This is in line with Baktash and Thalib (2019) which state that the survival of a company depends on the loyalty of its customers. This explains that customer loyalty goes beyond what people usually think.

2.2 Brand Image

Brand image is a positive impression of the brand of a product that the company instills in the minds of consumers, such as product reputation and superiority, and is easy to recognize. Brand image is an association (perception) that exists in the minds of consumers towards a brand. The association with a brand will be stronger if it is based on experience and gets a lot of information. The formation of the image of the association (perception) is the basis for buying decisions and even brand loyalty by consumers according to Fatema and Masum, (2015). Brand image is a perception and belief about a brand that is reflected by brand associations that exist in consumer memory. Rangkuty (2016) states that brand image are a set of brand associations that are formed and stick in the minds of consumers. Consumers who always use a certain brand when they want to buy an item usually look for the same type or item. According to Peter

and Olson (2013), brand image includes knowledge and belief in brand attributes (cognitive aspects). According to Clow and Donald (2018), brand image reflects the feelings consumers and businesses have about the entire organization as well as individual products or product lines. According to Schiffman and Wisenblit (2015), brand image is a different image that a brand has in the minds of consumers. Kotler and Armstrong (2018) state that brand image is a set of consumer beliefs about various brands. According to Kotler & Keller (2016) defines brand image as the perceptions and beliefs held by consumers, as reflected in the associations held in consumer memory. This means that these are the perceptions and beliefs held by consumers, which are reflected or embedded in the minds and memories of the consumers themselves. And Witama and Keni (2020) define brand image as a product that has characteristics that are liked by consumers. Brand image can be described as something that can make an impression on the minds of consumers.

2.3 Price

Prices are not just numbers on the label of a package or a store shelf; they take many forms and perform many functions. Alma (2014) states that price are the value of an item expressed in money. Furthermore Tjiptono (2017) argues that price is the only element of the marketing mix that generates income, while the other elements generate or constitute costs. Price is defined as the amount of money (monetary unit) and/or other aspects (non-monetary) that contain certain utilities needed to obtain a product. Kotler and Keller (2016) stated that price as the amount of money charged for a product or service, or the sum of values that customers exchange for benefits of having or using the product service. Or price can be defined broadly as the amount of value that consumers exchange for the benefits of having and using a product or service that enables a company to earn a reasonable profit by being paid for the customer value it creates. According to Lupiyoadi (2013), price is a means of providing value to consumers and influencing product image and consumer decisions to buy. Suparyanto and Rosad (2015) argue that price is the amount of something that has value, which is generally in the form of money that must be sacrificed to obtain a product. In line with that, Daryanto (2013) defines that price is the amount of money billed for a product or the amount of value exchanged by consumers for the benefits of owning or using a product. This is then confirmed by the opinion of Alma (2014) that price is the value of an item expressed in money.

2.4 Product Quality

According to Sunyoto (2015), product quality is the totality of product descriptions and characteristics that depend on their ability to satisfy the needs that customers want, as well as according to Prastiwi and Rivai (2022). Customers will be satisfied after buying and using these products with good quality according to Choiriah (2019). Assauri (2017) says that product quality is the factors contained in an item or result that causes the item or result to be in accordance with the purpose for which the item or result is intended. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2018), to determine that product quality is good, there are 8 criteria that must be met, namely: performance, feature, reliability, conformance, durability, serviceability, aesthetics, and perceived quality. If these eight dimensions are at least good, then the product is considered good by consumers, but if this is not met, there is

no need to expect that consumers will judge the product as good. Performance is a functional aspect contained in the product and is the main characteristic that is considered by customers in buying goods. Features are dimensions related to performance aspects that support the basic functions of a product and are related to product choice and development. Basically, reliability is the chance of a product being free from product failures while carrying out its functions, meaning that this dimension is related to the consistency of product performance. Conformance is the suitability of product performance with the standards stated in a product. This is a kind of promise that must be fulfilled by the product (Kotler and Armstrong, 2018). Durability shows the age of the product, namely the number of uses of a product before the product is replaced or damaged. Serviceability is the extent to which the product can be repaired. Aesthetic is about the appearance of a product that makes consumers like it. The point is that aesthetics concerns the presentation of products that can be assessed by the five senses (taste, smell, sound, and so on). Meanwhile, perceived quality relates to consumers' evaluation of images, brands or advertisements as well as corporate responsibility. According to (Kotler and Armstrong, 2018), products with well-known brands are usually perceived to be of higher quality than brands that are not well-known, so that each product always tries to build its brand so that it has high brand equity.

2.5 Service Quality

Service quality is a comparison of the level of service provided by the company compared to consumer expectations. According to Utami (2017), quality can be viewed broadly as excellence or privilege and can be defined as the delivery of services that are relatively special or superior to customer expectations. Service is also defined as activities, benefits, and satisfaction from something offered in sales. According to Barnes (2014), service quality is a consumer's assessment of the reliability and superiority of the service as a whole, consumer will make comparisons between what they provide and what they get. According to (Asana, 2008), components in business services cannot be separated both service companies and trading companies. Meanwhile, according to Sunyoto (2015), service quality is centered on efforts to fulfill consumer needs and desires and the accuracy of their delivery to offset consumer expectations, namely:

- a. There is conformity between expectations and management perceptions.
- b. There is compatibility between perceptions of consumer expectations and employee work standards.
- c. There is conformity between employee work standards and the services provided with the services promised
- d. There is conformity between the services received and what consumers expect. Utami (2017) said that service standards should be based on customer perceptions compared to internal operations

2.7 Research Hypothesis

A schematic diagram of the relationship between the variables in this study is shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Effect Relationships between Research Variables

- 1 Price (X₁) has a significant effect on customer loyalty (Y)
- 2 Product quality (X₂) has a significant effect on customer loyalty (Y)
- 3 Service quality (X₃) has a significant effect on customer loyalty (Y)
- 4 Price (X₁) has a significant effect on brand image (Z)
- 5 Product quality (X₂) has a significant effect on brand image (Z)
- 6 Service quality (X₃) has a significant effect on brand image (Z)
7. Brand image (Z) has a significant effect on customer loyalty (Y)
8. Brand image (Z) significantly mediates the effect of price (X₁) on customer loyalty (Y)
9. Brand image (Z) significantly mediates the effect of product quality (X₂) on customer loyalty (Y)
- 10 Brand image (Z) significantly mediates the effect of service quality (X₃) on customer loyalty (Y)

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach. Data was collected by distributing questionnaires with a Likert scale to a sample consisting of 134 respondents, where the sample was selected using non-probability sampling (Sugiono, 2015: 84). The research data were analyzed using a structural equation (SEM) model based on partial least squares (PLS) which aims to test the direct effect and to measure the strength of the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable studied in this research.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

The calculation results for the Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model) in this study are as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 4: The Results of Calculating the Value of Loading Factor for Each Variable

Based on Figure 4 above it appears that all variables have met the validity requirements with a loading factor value for all indicators are > 0.7 . Thus, the next test can be carried out.

Construct Reliability Test

Table 1: Construct Reliability and Validity

Sampel 172, Var 5, Kuesioner 9,9,9,11,10.txt *Sampel 172,varibel 5.splsm PLS Algorithm (Run No. 2)

Construct Reliability and Validity

Matrix	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extract...	Copy
	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted ...	
X1	0.892	0.894	0.914	0.571	
X2	0.903	0.904	0.922	0.596	
X3	0.908	0.908	0.924	0.577	
Y	0.921	0.922	0.934	0.586	
Z	0.927	0.927	0.938	0.603	

The results of the analysis shown in Table 1 above show that the AVE value of each latent variable is > 0.5 and the composite reliability value and Cronbach's alpha value for each latent variable is greater than 0.7, so it can be concluded that the variable indicators are able to measure well.

Measurement Model Analysis (Inner Model)

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 2: Value of R-Square

Sampel 172, Var 5, Kuesioner 9,9,9,11,10.txt *Sampel 172,varibel 5.splsm P

R Square

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y	0.972	0.971
Z	0.940	0.939

Based on table 2 it is known that the adjusted R-Square value for the customer loyalty variable is 0.971 or 97.1% and the remaining 2.9% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study, while the adjusted R-Square value for the brand variable image is 0.939 or 93.9% and the remaining 6.1% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Predictive Relevance (Q²)

The value of Q² has the same meaning as the coefficient of determination R-Square. The value of Q-square (Q²) is greater than 0 indicating the model has predictive relevance. On the other hand, the value of Q² is less than 0 indicating that the model has less predictive relevance or

in other words, if all the values of Q2 are higher, the model is considered to be more compatible with the data. Calculation of the value of Q2 can be done as follows.

$$Q2 = 1 - (1-R^2_1) (1-R^2_2) \dots (R_n^2)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (1-0.971) (1-0,939)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (0,029) (0,061)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (0.0017)$$

$$Q2 = 0.998$$

Based on the results above, the value of Q2 is 0.998. So it can be concluded that all variables in this study, namely employee creativity, transformational leadership, employee performance, and job satisfaction contributed 99.8% of the original data in the structural model. Then the remaining 0.2% needs to be developed in addition to this research variable.

Effect Size (F2)

Effect size (F2) is determining the kindness of the model and also to find out whether the predictor variable has a weak, sufficient or strong effect at the structural level.

Hypothesis Test

Table 3: Direct Effects between Variables

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviatio...	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X2 -> Z	0.433	0.437	0.041	10.656	0.000
X1 -> Z	0.459	0.458	0.047	9.698	0.000
Z -> Y	0.410	0.411	0.043	9.625	0.000
X3 -> Y	0.412	0.410	0.044	9.390	0.000
X1 -> Y	0.186	0.187	0.043	4.384	0.000
X3 -> Z	0.111	0.109	0.058	1.909	0.057

From Table 3 above it can be seen whether or not there is an effect between the variables in this study where the complete description according to the results of data analysis is as follows:

1. Price (X1) directly has Significant Effect on Customer Loyalty (Y)

Price directly has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty. This result can be seen from the significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This means that the higher the price, the more customer loyalty will increase in the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. The results of this study are in line with the results of a study conducted by Saputri (2019) which indicates that price has an effect on customer loyalty and is also in line with the results of a study by Kurniasih (2012) which shows that price has an effect on customer loyalty. Similar results were also shown by Soriton's study which indicated that the direct effect of price on

loyalty was greater than the indirect effect. Similarly, the study by Tampi and Walangitan (2021) shows that price has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty. Likewise the results of the study by Pratama, Susanti and Purwaningrat (2021) which show that price has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty.

2. Product Quality (X2) directly has Significant Effect on Customer Loyalty (Y)

The results show that product quality has a significant effect on customer loyalty. This is known from the significance value for the product quality variable of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. So it can be concluded that the higher the product quality, the customer loyalty will increase. These results are consistent with the results of a study conducted by Ginting and Sitorus (2022) which showed that product quality has a significant effect on customer loyalty. Also in line with these results is the study of Rakasena (2020) which shows that the direct effect of product quality on customer loyalty is significant. The findings of this study are also in line with the results of Hartadi's study (2018) which proves product quality has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty. Similar results are also indicated by the results of the study by Prastiwi and Rivai (2022) which state that product quality has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty. Similarly, the study of Zaw and Chaipoopirutana (2014) also shows that product quality has a positive and significant correlation to customer loyalty.

3. Service Quality (X3) Directly has Significant Effect on Customer Loyalty (Y)

Service quality directly has an effect on customer loyalty in the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. This can be seen from the P value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This means that if the quality of service increases, customer loyalty will increase. These results are consistent with a study conducted by Saputri (2019) which shows that service quality and price affect customer loyalty. Also in line with these results are the results of the study of Soriton, Tampi and Walangitan (2021) which show that there is a significant positive effect of service quality on customer loyalty. Similar results are shown by the studies of Putri, Suharyono and Fanani (2015), and Pratama, Susanti and Purwaningrat (2021) which state that service quality has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty. It is also similar to the results of the study by Waskito and Sudjatno (2016) which show that service quality has a direct or indirect effect on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Service quality has a direct effect on customer loyalty which is also confirmed by a study conducted by Saidin, Rahman and Hamid (2020) which states that the elements of service quality show a strong effect on customer loyalty, especially after-sales service. Furthermore, Rahman and Saidin (2021) state that there is a significant relationship between customer loyalty and service quality. In contrast to the results of the studies mentioned above, the results of the study by Sebastian, Rojuaniah (2020) show that service quality has no effect on customer loyalty.

4. Price (X1) Directly has Significant Effect on Brand Image (Z)

Prices directly affect Brand Image (Z) in the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. The P value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05, this means that price has an effect on brand image, and these results are in accordance with the results of a study conducted by Rafael Billy Leksono (2017) which shows that price has an effect on brand image.

5. Product Quality (X2) Directly has Significant Effect on Brand Image (Z)

Product quality directly has a significant positive effect on brand image. This result can be seen from the significance value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This means that if the product quality improves, the brand image will significantly increase in the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. The results of this study are in accordance with studies that examine the factors that influence brand image by Schiffman and Kanuk (1997) in Nedi (2008:24), and it is also stated that the factors forming brand image are quality, reliability, benefits, service, risk, price, and image owned by the brand.

6. Service Quality (X3) Directly Has No Effect on Brand Image (Z)

Service quality has no effect on Brand Image. These results can be seen from the significance value of 0.057 greater than 0.05. The results of this study are not in accordance with a study conducted by Darmawan which states that service quality has a positive effect on brand image.

Table 4: Indirect Effects between Variables

	Original ...	Sample ...	Standard ...	T Statistic...	P Values
X1 -> Z -> Y	0.188	0.188	0.027	7.051	0.000
X2 -> Z -> Y	0.178	0.180	0.023	7.607	0.000
X3 -> Z -> Y	0.045	0.045	0.025	1.803	0.072

7. Indirect Effect of Price (X1) on Customer Loyalty (Y) through Brand Image (Z)

Brand Image (Z) has a significant effect in mediating the effect of price (X1) on customer loyalty (Y). This can be seen from the significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05, where the effect is 0.188 or 18.8%. This means that the contribution to price (X1) in increasing customer loyalty (Y) is 18.8%

8. Indirect Effect of Product Quality (X2) on Customer Quality (Y) through Brand Image (Z)

Brand Image (Z) has a significant effect in mediating product quality (X2) on customer loyalty (Y). This can be seen from the significance value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05, where the effect is 0.178 or 17.8%. This means that the contribution to product quality (X2) in increasing customer loyalty (Y) is 17.8%.

9. Indirect Effect of Service Quality (X3) on Customer Loyalty (Y) through Brand Image (Z)

Brand Image (Z) has no significant effect in mediating service quality (X3) on customer loyalty (Y). This can be seen from the significance value of 0.072 which is greater than 0.05, where the effect size is 0.045 or 4.5%. This means that the contribution to service quality (X3) in increasing customer loyalty (Y) is 4.5%.

5. CONCLUSION

The conclusion that can be drawn based on the results of this study is that there is a direct significant positive effect of the four variables namely brand image, price, product quality, and service quality on customer loyalty, and it is also concluded that price and product quality directly have a significant effect on brand image, but service quality does not have a significant effect on brand image in the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. Furthermore, brand image indirectly mediates the effect of price and service quality on customer loyalty, but brand image cannot mediate the effect of service quality on customer loyalty in the Toyota Automotive Industry in Medan. Bottom of Form

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